

A STUDY OF EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS AFFILIATED TO SHIVAJI UNIVERSITY KOLHAPUR

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Abstract

Employability is the buzz word in the market. The success or outcome of Higher education is measured in terms of the placement of the students. The demands of market are changing with tremendous speed due to globalization. The market is open to all and survive you need to be fit for the purpose. People invest in education to acquire good job and get back the returns they have invested for education.

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to measure the employability skills among the student teachers. The descriptive survey method was adopted for the present study and the data was collected from the teacher educators pursuing in aided colleges. The study reveals that there is no significant difference in the employability skills among the student teachers from different district. Student teachers are high on Lifelong learning Leadership skills and low at Academic Communication skills and ICT Skills.

Key words : *Employability Skills , Student teachers*

Human beings are the most intelligent of all living beings on planet earth. They possess the unique gift of the dynamic brain and intellect through which they acquire knowledge. This endeavour of man of acquiring knowledge is termed as education. Education is a purposefully designed process which enables the healthy and harmonious development of individuals so that they are transformed into productive, successful and well – adjusted citizens of the society

The concept of employability has been dynamic and travelled long way. It was traced in the year 1950 and was with reference to Socio-medical, gradually the concept got changed as per the time and various revolution. At the initial level the concept of Employability was coined and influence in the period of industrialisation.

Naira Chenicheri Sid, PatilAru (2009) revealed that university graduates do not possess important skills required by employers, such as communication, decision-making, problem-solving, leadership, emotional intelligence, social ethics skills as well as the ability to work with people of different backgrounds. This paper elaborates on the missing links between engineering graduate attributes and employers' expectations.

Bremner A M Pauline (2018) concludes that the FM alumni suggested some changes were required in relation to group/soft and digital skills within the degree programme. The additional employer research added to the debate on the importance of digital skills and that future employees must come to jobs ‘digitally ready’.

Weligamage Susima S.(2011) discussed existing research findings on studies and practices of employability skills on eight aspects as, definitions of employability, employability skills and employer needs, expectations of employers and university students, matching employer needs, the nature of employability, international perspective on employability and employability as key performance Indicator.

Valerie Cotronei-Baird (2017) concluded in the paper integrating employability skills in the university curriculum: Setting a research agenda that responds to stakeholders’ expectation that employability skills are now considered an important graduate learning outcome, it is necessary to investigate to what extent academics integrate employability skills in the university curriculum.

Gill Robert (2018) Employability has become an important focus for graduates and employers in Australia, as many universities contend with the notion of developing knowledgeable and problem-solving graduates who are workforce ready practitioners.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

A STUDY

In the present research, the word ‘**A Study**’ refers to *a research investigation* undertaken to discover new information on the topic selected.

Employability Skills

In the present research, the employability skills refers to the Pedagogical skills, ICT Skills, Leadership skills, Creative thinking skills, Collaborative skills, Critical thinking skills, Life Long learning Skills and Academic Communication skills.

i. **Pedagogical skills** refers to the skills like Classroom Management skills, Creating a Comfortable Learning Environment, good in Knowledge about curriculum, developing Learning Material, developing Lesson Plans, designing tools/ technique to Evaluate Performance developing positive discipline among students and framing objectives and outcomes

ii.**ICT Skills** refers to the skills like computer based Testing for evaluation, word processing skills, using web based technology , web navigation skills, web based application for education, computer installing computer software onto a computer system, social networking sites, Spreadsheet skills, Educational Copyright knowledge and knowing web resources for education.

iii. Leadership skills refers to the skills like Confidence Building of others, directing to achieve the task /target, communication, persuading, taking initiative, going along with new people, comfortable doing arithmetic, passionate about teaching, accountable in my profession accepting various point of view.

iv. Creative thinking skills refers to the skills like Creating innovative Assignments, creating new things, Analytical thinking, contribute very well in team work, writing, different forms of creative arts(Visual, Arts, Photographs), good articulation, designing creative lesson plan, reasoning, creating something new.

v. Collaborative skills refers to the skills like contributing in Education Plans, dealing with issues among colleagues, going along very well in the team, believing in code of conduct of the profession, completing the task within time, arguments, reliable, listening feelings, opinion and ideas of other, giving critical constructive feedback, contributing very well in team.

vi. Critical thinking Skills refers to the skills like Critical Thinking, gathering information systematically to establish facts and principles, contributing own ideas effectively in group situations, putting things in logical way, unbiased, rational thinking, believing change and molding myself accordingly, critically analyzing the content to be taught, reflective thinking, interference/interpretation.

vii. Life long learning skills refers to the skills like new learning, portraying skills in teaching learning process, reflective learning, believing in change and molding accordingly, believing in Lifelong learning, Problem solving, learning new style and techniques, managing information, curiosity and adaptation.

viii. Academic Communication skills refers to the skills like note making skill, using the words and structures used to express ideas, presenting ideas effectively and formally in a scholastic environment, interacting and convincing stakeholders of education, structured communication used in pedagogical settings, writing formal emails/ reports, Administrative academic communication (Reports, Presentations), reading academic text, keen listening in academic context, reflective writing.

Student Teachers

In the present research, student teachers refer to the students pursuing Bachelor of Education to be a future school teacher.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

- 1) To compare the Employability skills among the student teachers pursuing aided teacher education institutions affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur
- 2) To measure the status of employability skills among the student teachers of
 - i. SMT College of Education, Kolhapur
 - ii. Azad College of Education, Satara

- iii. S P Shah College of Education, Sangli based on following indicators
- i. Pedagogical skills
 - ii. ICT Skills
 - iii. Leadership skills
 - iv. Creative thinking Skills
 - v. Collaborative thinking skills
 - vi. Critical thinking skills
 - vii. Life long learning skills
 - viii. Academic Communication Skills

3) To make suggestions based on the results of this research to enhance the Employability skills among the student teachers.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

The data will be collected from the student teachers pursuing Bachelor of Education for the academic year 2018-19 of the aided teacher education institution affiliated to the Shivaji University, Kolhapur

NEED FOR THE RESEARCH

Higher and professional education is linked to placement in the current context . Today in the era of globalization the form and nature of skills required for the profession are changing tremendously. Teaching profession has been included in service sector and as per the need and demand of the market the form of services need to upgraded to achieve the need and demand of market. Also, there had been very few researches on this topic in India Therefore, the researcher felt the need of studying parental involvement in the academics of their wards.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

The research will be significant for,

1) Student teacher

This research will help the student teacher get aware of employability skills along with their own status.

2) Teacher education institutions

This research will help the teacher education institutions to know the status of their student with reference to their employability.

The findings of the study may open new horizon of the research area and will also help the policy maker to design the policy as per the need of hour.

SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH

The conclusions of this research will be applicable to the teacher education institutions of affiliated to the Shivaji University, Kolhapur. .

Research Design

The present research aimed at quantifying data and generalizing results from a sample to the population of interest hence the quantitative approach of research was adopted. The descriptive survey method was employed in this research.

Sampling Design

The 3 aided teacher education colleges (One from each district) affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur were chosen and the incidental purposive random sampling was adopted to collect the data from teacher education institutions. The sample size of the data was 96.

Data Gathering Tools

The following tools were used for gathering the data required for the studying consultation with experts keeping in mind the objectives of the study.

- i) Researcher Made Employability Skills Scale

Procedure for Data Collection

In order to collect data the formal permission from the Principal of the Teacher Education Institution was taken by giving them all information and purpose of the study... After receiving the permission, the researcher began with the data collection from the Teacher education Institutions.

Statistical Tools used in the Present Study

The statistical tools used for the quantitative analysis of the data obtained during the study are as follows:

- i) ANOVA
- ii) Percentage

Analysis

The data obtained from the questionnaire was scrutinized, coded and punched with the help of the computer. The data was tabulated and objective – wise analysis of the data was done using Anova and percentage.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA

The data collected for the present study has been analyzed and interpreted objective wise as follows:

Objective No. 1

To compare the employability skills among the student teachers of aided teacher education institutions affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Table No. 1

SMT	X2	Azad	X2	SPS	X2
217	47089	215	46225	310	96100
252	63504	273	74529	270	72900
222	49284	204	41616	289	83521
277	76729	285	81225	312	97344
157	24649	221	48841	253	64009
255	65025	273	74529	302	91204
227	51529	264	69696	311	96721
229	52441	241	58081	311	96721
208	43264	203	41209	312	97344
245	60025	234	54756	178	31684
254	64516	260	67600	130	16900
217	47089	279	77841	151	22801
264	69696	249	62001	188	35344
244	59536	227	51529	186	34596
181	32761	242	58564	316	99856
260	67600	189	35721	308	94864
182	33124	302	91204	289	83521
274	75076	225	50625	307	94249
232	53824	305	93025	210	44100
233	54289	316	99856	275	75625
223	49729	273	74529	275	75625
163	26569	308	94864	196	38416
263	69169	301	90601	186	34596
206	42436	241	58081	294	86436
205	42025	302	91204	268	71824
178	31684	109	11881	265	70225
210	44100	94	8836	265	70225
252	63504	186	34596	149	22201
209	43681	296	87616	234	54756
235	55225	193	37249	235	55225

238	56644	291	84681	301	90601
243	59049	298	88804	131	17161

Grand Sum=	23161
General Mean	241.2604167
Step 1 Correction Term C	5587832.51
Step 2 Total Sum of Sqr	74424.48958
Step 3 Sum of sqr among means	10332.33333
Step 4 Sum of squares within conditions	64092.15625

Df	sum of Sqr	Msqr	Sd
2	10332.33333	5166.167	
93	64092.15625	689.163	3165.7197
95	74424.48958		
	7.496291714		

F=	7.496291714			df=2	0.05	99.2
				df=93	0.01	19.2

Observation and Interpretation

The obtain F value 7.50 is less than the tabulated value 19.18 at 0.05 level hence there is no significant difference in the student teacher employability skills among the teacher education institutions affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

There is no significant difference in the student teacher employability skills among the teacher education institutions affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Status of Employability Skills among Student-teachers of Shree Maharani Tarabai Government College of Education, Kolhapur

Table No. 2

Sr. No.	Components	No. of Sample	%
1	Pedagogical Skills	32	69.14
2	ICT Skills		66.44
3	Leadership Skills		75.23
4	Creative Thinking Skills		70.39
5	Collaborative Skills		72.26
6	Critical Thinking Skills		71.32
7	Life Long Learning Skills		76.17
8	Academic Communication Skills		65.85

Observation and Interpretation

From the above table No. 4.2 it is observed that among the employability skills acquired by the student teachers are Lifelong learning skills (76.17), Leadership skills (75.23), Collaborative skills (72.26), Creative thinking skills (70.39), Critical thinking skills (71.32) Pedagogical skills (69.14), ICT Skills (66.44). Academic communication skills (65.85).

Interpretation

From the above observation it can be interpreted that the student teachers of SMT Government College of Education are highest on lifelong learning skills and low in Academic Communication Skills.

Employability Skills among Student Teachers of Shree Maharani Tarabai

Objective 2.2

To measure the status of Employability Skills among Student-teachers Azad College of Education, Satara.

**Status of Employability Skills among Student-teachers of
Azad College of Education, Satara**

Table No. 3

Sr. No.	Components	No. of Sample	%
1	Pedagogical Skills	32	75.94
2	ICT Skills		70.60
3	Leadership Skills		80.40
4	Creative Thinking Skills		78.13
5	Collaborative Skills		79.06
6	Critical Thinking Skills		78.05
7	Life Long Learning Skills		83.50
8	Academic Communication Skills		71.30

Observation and Interpretation

From the above table No. 4.3it is observed that among the employability skills acquired by the student teachers are Lifelong learning skills (83.50), Leadership skills (80.40) , Collaborative skills(79.06) , Creative thinking skills (78.13) , Critical thinking skills (78.05) Pedagogical skills(75.94), Academic communication skills (71.30) ICT Skills (70.60).

Interpretation

From the above observation it can be interpreted that the student teachers of Azad College of Education, Satara are highest on lifelong learning skills and low in ICT Skills.

Objective 4

To measure the status of Employability Skills among Student-teachers of Shreemati Putlaben Shah College of Education, Sangli

**Status of Employability Skills among Student-teachers of
ShreematiPutlaben Shah College of Education, Sangli**

Table No.4

Sr. No.	Components	No. of Sample	
1	Pedagogical Skills	32	79.3
2	ICT Skills		67.5
3	Leadership Skills		81.41
4	Creative Thinking Skills		74.69
5	Collaborative Skills		76.72
6	Critical Thinking Skills		70.78
7	Life Long Learning Skills		74.53
8	Academic Communication Skills		60.78
	Total		73.22

Observation and Interpretation

From the above table No. 4.4 it is observed that among the employability skills acquired by the student teachers are Leadership skills (81.41), Pedagogical skills (79.3), Collaborative skills(76.72), Creative thinking skills (74.69), Life long learning skills (74.53), Critical thinking skills (70.78) (ICT skills (67.5), Academic communication skills (60.78).

Interpretation

From the above observation it can be interpreted that the student teachers of Shreemati Putlaben Shah College of Education, Sangli are highest on Leadership skills and low in Academic Communication Skills.

Findings of the Study

There is no significant difference in the student teacher employability skills among the teacher education institutions affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Student teachers of SMT Government College of Education are highest on lifelong learning skills and low in Academic Communication Skills.

Student teachers of Azad College of Education, Satara are highest on lifelong learning skills and low in ICT Skills.

Student teachers of Shreemati Putlaben Shah College of Education, Sangli are highest on Leadership skills and low in Academic Communication Skills.

Implications

There is urgent need to add on the 21st Century skills as they are essentials in the contemporary competitive world for the teacher educators. The contemporary learners are digital natives and broadly differ in their learning styles. The work profile of educational organization had been changed and the student teachers need to upgrade them accordingly. The pedagogical skills need to keep abreast and new learning style based on connectivism has to inserted and implement in the curriculum. The Academic communication skills are essential and its horizon has been broaden from verbal, non verbal to online. The ICT skills need to upgrade from PPT to learning platforms and web based learning.

Valerie Cotronei-Baird (2017) concluded in the paper integrating employability skills in the university curriculum: Setting a research agenda that responds to stakeholders'

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